

Investigating the Antibacterial Potential of Nitrated Quinazolinones: Synthesis and Spectroscopic Characterization

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ABSTRACT

Quinazolinones are important heterocyclic compounds with significant medical applications. Their derivatives are essential in developing drugs for antibacterial, analgesic, antimalarial, anticancer, antihistaminic, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and anti-tubercular uses. This study focused on quinazolinones, the most biologically active derivatives, to enhance their antibacterial potential. We aimed to increase the active sites by nitrating quinazolinones and then reducing them to amino derivatives. Various nitration methods were explored, with HNO₃/H₂SO₄ yielding the best results at low temperatures. Spectroscopic studies (FTIR and UV) confirmed the successful synthesis of amino derivatives, indicating a potential increase in biological activity.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds in vital biological molecules play significant roles in agriculture and pharmaceuticals (Sarfraz et al., 2019; Hagan et al., 2000). Quinazoline and quinazolinone are important heterocyclic compounds with medicinal properties (Mhaske et al., 2006). Quinazoline, a nitrogen-containing fused pyrimidine ring system, has been extensively studied for its pharmaceutical potential (Sarfraz et al., 2017). Derivatives of quinazoline exhibit a variety of biological activities, including anticancer, antioxidant, anticonvulsant, antitubercular, antiHIV, antiviral, analgesic, antiinflammatory, and antimicrobial effects (Shetha and Wijdan, 2013; Vagdevi et al., 2012; Patel et al., 2010; Abid and Ahmed, 2013; Pati and Banerjee, 2013; Krishnan et al., 2011; Alagarsamy et al., 2003; Saravanan et al., 2010; Rudrapal and De, 2013). Quinazoline derivatives are also valuable in industrial chemistry (Rajput and Mishra, 2012). This research aims to synthesize amino derivatives of quinazolinone and evaluate their biological activities.

Quinazoline derivatives are found in over 150 naturally occurring alkaloids from plants, animals, and microorganisms. In the 1860s, 2-cyanoquinazolinone was synthesized from anthranilic acid and cyanogen (Mhaske et al., 2006). Interest in quinazolinone chemistry grew after discovering quinazolinone alkaloid from the Asian plant *Dichroa febrifuge*, used in traditional Chinese malaria treatment (Koepfly et al., 1947). A derivative with sedative-hypnotic effects was later prepared in the search for more effective quinazolinone-based drugs (Mhaske et al., 2006; Amin et al., 1970).

In the early 1900s, 2cyano3,4dihydro4oxoquinazoline was synthesized from anthranilic acid and cyanogen (Asif, 2014). Gabriel extensively studied quinazoline's structure and preparation methods, and Widdege first proposed the name quinazoline (Rajput and Mishra, 2012). Other names include phenmiazine, 1,3diazanaphthaline, and 5,6benzopyrimidine. In 1951, the synthetic drug Methaqualone, with hypnotic effects, was developed, sparking significant research into quinazolinone derivatives (Kacker et al., 1951).

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Quinazolinone, an oxidized form of quinazoline, contains a tworing structure with pyrimidine and benzene rings and a keto group. Quinazolinone derivatives are classified based on the keto group position into three types: quinazolin4one, quinazolin2one, and quinazoline2,4dione (Mahato et al., 2011).

Quinazolin4one

Quinazolin2one

Quinazoline2,4dione

In 2006, Tan identified new alkaloids including chaetominine from *Chaetomium* on *Adenophora axiliflora*, active against colon cancer and leukemia (Kshirsagar, 2015). *Aspergillus* produced isochaetominines showing activity against K/Na ATPase. *Rhizophora stylosa* leaves hosted *Aspergillus nidulans*, a source of quinazoline derivative retarding brine shrimp activity. *Neosartorya siamensis* produced tritoqualine and dione, but without significant cytotoxicity.

Quinazoline derivatives are the basis of many medicines, known for their therapeutic properties (Sarfranz et al., 2018). They have applications as antineoplastic, antipsychotic, antihypertensive, and antidepressant agents, and some also exhibit sedative, analgesic, antiinflammatory, antifungal, and antibacterial activities (Pati et al., 2013).

Quinazolinone derivatives exhibit antibacterial activities against various bacteria. They affect grampositive bacteria like *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus*, and gramnegative bacteria like *Certium* and *Escherichia coli* (Patel et al., 2011). Some derivatives, such as acetamide, are more effective than common antibiotics like ampicillin (Cakici et al., 2010). Demonstrated compounds like 4(6methyl4phenylquinazolin2yl) morpholine show greater activity against *P. aeruginosa*, *S. sonnei*, and *E. faecalis* compared to ciprofloxacin. Other derivatives, such as

4(4(isopropylphenyl)6methylquinazolin2yl) morpholine, are potent against *K. pneumonia* (Alafeefy et al., 2011). Additionally, quinazolinone derivatives display antifungal properties against *B. subtilis*, *S. cerevisiae*, and *C. albicans* (Jatav et al., 2008).

Quinazolinone Based Drugs

Quinazolinone derivatives have significant medicinal importance and are used in various pharmacological activities. Some notable quinazolinonebased drugs include:

Drug Name	Description	References
Cloroqualone	Sedative and cough suppressant, similar to Metaqualone.	(Chaudhary et al., 2018)
Febrifuge	Antimalarial extracted from <i>Dichroa febrifuge</i> leaves in 1948.	(Chen et al., 2006)
Ketanserin	Serotonin antagonist sold as Sufrexal, used to treat chronic hypertension.	(Sundrud et al., 2009)

Diproqualone	Analgesic and antihistamine, used for neuralgia, insomnia, and arthritis.	(Ishikawa et al., 1994)
Afloqualone	Muscle relaxant and sedative developed in Japan in 1980.	(Ishikawa et al., 1994)
Halofuginone	Isolated from <i>Dichroa febrifuga</i> , inhibits immune cells and treats autoimmune disorders.	(Gnainsky et al., 2004)
Fenquizone	Diuretic sold as Idrolone, used for hypertension and edema.	(Mackay et al., 2001)
Raltitrexed	Inhibits DNA and RNA synthesis, used to treat colorectal cancer, sold as Tomudex.	(Widemann et al., 1999)

Table 1: Overview of various quinazolinonebased drugs, highlighting their medicinal uses and key properties. Each entry includes the drug's name, a brief description of its pharmacological activity, and relevant references for further reading.

This article aims to synthesize an "Amino derivative of quinazolinone" using different nitrating and reducing agents, and to characterize the synthesized product using various techniques. The goal is to identify the most efficient synthesis methods for these derivatives. Quinazolinone derivatives are widely used in medicine for their antibacterial, analgesic, antimalarial, anticancer, antihistaminic, antiinflammatory, antifungal, and antitubercular properties. These compounds serve as raw materials for synthesizing various biologically active drugs. The medicinal activity of quinazolinones can be enhanced by attaching an active amino group, improving their binding with body enzymes. This research focuses on optimizing the synthesis and characterization of amino derivatives of quinazolinone to enhance their therapeutic efficacy.

Materials and Methods

This study utilized a quantitative experimental research design to synthesize, nitrate, and reduce quinazolinone derivatives and evaluate their potential antibacterial properties. The experiments were systematically conducted in phases.

- || Solvents were distilled and stored with drying agents.
- || Reaction progress was monitored using TLC.
- || Products were purified and analyzed using FTIR and melting point determination.

Key materials used include 2,2dimethyl2,3dihydroquinazolin4one, water (H₂O), nitrating agents such as nitric acid (HNO₃), potassium nitrate (KNO₃), and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). Sodium bicarbonate (Na₂CO₃) was used for neutralization. Reduction agents included tin (Sn), hydrochloric acid (HCl), stannous chloride (SnCl₂), and ethanol (C₂H₅OH). Solvents for chromatography (n-hexane, ethyl acetate, methanol) were sourced from Merck, distilled, and stored with drying agents.

Analytical Techniques

1. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)

Reaction progress was monitored using TLC with silica gel plates as the stationary phase and various solvent ratios (nhexane, ethyl acetate, methanol) as the mobile phase. The developed chromatograms were visualized under a UV lamp (254365 nm), and R_f values were calculated.

- **Stationary Phase:** Silica gel plates
- **Mobile Phase:** Various solvent ratios of nhexane, ethyl acetate, and methanol
- **Detection:** UV lamp (254365 nm)
- **R_f Calculation:**

$$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance travelled by component from base line}}{\text{Distance traveled by solvent from baseline}}$$

2. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR was used to identify functional groups in the product, with spectra recorded in the 4004000 cm⁻¹ range using KBr pellets.

|| **Range:** 400-4000 cm⁻¹

|| **Method:** KBr pellets

|| **Recorded Units:** cm⁻¹

3. Melting Point (M.P.)

Melting points were recorded using the open capillary method with a Gallen Kamp apparatus and compared to literature values.

Experiment 1:

Synthesis of 2,2dimethyl2,3dihydroquinazolin4(1H)one

The compound was synthesized by reacting acetone with 2aminobenzamide, catalyzed by Lewis acid. The product was monitored by TLC, with R_f values of 0.8 (substrate) and 0.52 (product). The melting point was 180±5°C.

FTIR (KBr): NH 3263 cm⁻¹, CH 2968 cm⁻¹, C=O 1629 cm⁻¹, CN 1292 cm⁻¹

Experiment 2:

Nitration of Quinazolinone

1. 6hour Nitration

Quinazolinone was nitrated using KNO_3 and H_2SO_4 . The product was a brown solid with an intermediate yield of 65% and a melting point of $245\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

FTIR (KBr): NH 3271 cm^{-1} , C=O 1627 cm^{-1} , NO_2^+ 1500 cm^{-1} , CN 1340 cm^{-1}

2. 5hour Nitration

Using a different nitrating agent, the reaction was completed in 5 hours with a yield of 80% and a melting point of $260\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

FTIR (KBr): NH 3271 cm^{-1} , C=O 1622 cm^{-1} , NO_2^+ 1500 cm^{-1} , CN 1342 cm^{-1}

3. Enhanced Yield Nitration

By adjusting the reaction conditions, the yield was increased to 90% with a melting point of $240\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

FTIR (KBr): NH 3257 cm^{-1} , C=O 1624 cm^{-1} , NO_2^+ 1556 cm^{-1} , CN 1350 cm^{-1}

|| **6-Hour Nitration:** KNO_3 and H_2SO_4 , yield 65%, melting point $245\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

|| **5-Hour Nitration:** HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 , yield 80%, melting point $260\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

|| **6-Hour Nitration with Adjusted Quantities:** Yield 90%, melting point $240\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

Experiment 3:

Reduction of Nitro Group

1. Reduction with $\text{SnCl}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$

The reaction was refluxed for 2.5 hours, yielding a dark gray product with a melting point of $243\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ and a 69% yield.

FTIR (KBr): NH_2 3296 cm^{-1} , 3211 cm^{-1} , C=O 1629 cm^{-1} , CN 1344 cm^{-1}

2. Reduction with Sn/HCl

This method yielded a shiny yellow product with a melting point of $232\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and an 88% yield.

FTIR (KBr): NH_2 3267 cm^{-1} , 3257 cm^{-1} , $\text{C}=\text{O}$ 1622 cm^{-1} , CN 1317 cm^{-1}

3. Extended Reduction with $\text{SnCl}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$

A 3.5hour reflux yielded a yellow product with a melting point of $224\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and an 85.7% yield.

FTIR (KBr): NH_2 3163 cm^{-1} , 3178 cm^{-1} , $\text{C}=\text{O}$ 1622 cm^{-1} , CN 1321 cm^{-1}

4. Reduction with Zn/HCl

Yielded a yellow product with a melting point of $228\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and an 80% yield.

FTIR (KBr): NH_2 3251 cm^{-1} , 3234 cm^{-1} , $\text{C}=\text{O}$ 1622 cm^{-1} , CN 1315 cm^{-1}

5. Reduction with Zn/ NH_4Cl

Produced a blackish residue with a melting point of $228\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a 71% yield.

FTIR (KBr): NH_2 3197 cm^{-1} , 3169 cm^{-1} , $\text{C}=\text{O}$ 1629 cm^{-1} , CN 1377 cm^{-1}

|| **$\text{SnCl}_2/\text{Ethanol}$** : Yield 69%, melting point $243\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$.

|| **Sn/HCl** : Yield 88%, melting point $232\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$.

|| **$\text{SnCl}_2/\text{Ethanol at Higher Temp}$** : Yield 85.7%, melting point $224\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$.

|| **Zn/HCl** : Yield 80%, melting point $228\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$.

|| **$\text{Zn}/\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$** : Yield 71%, melting point $228\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The bar chart represents the yield, while the line graph represents the melting point for each experiment.

Graph 1: Yield and Melting Point of Nitrated and Reduced Quinazolinone Derivatives

Results

Quinazolinone, an important and flexible heterocyclic compound, is widely used in medicine due to its various biological activities, including antifungal, antimalarial, anti-inflammatory, antitubercular, antibacterial, anticancer, and analgesic properties. Modifying its structure can enhance its pharmacological effectiveness.

In this study, we synthesized nitro and amino derivatives of quinazolinone and characterized them using various analytical techniques. Initially, 2,2-dimethyl-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one was synthesized from acetone and 2-aminobenzamide using a Lewis acid catalyst. The reaction yielded bright yellow crystals.

Synthesis of 2,2-dimethyl-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (1)

FTIR Spectra of Compound 1

The infrared spectrum of compound (1) confirms its synthesis. Key peaks include 3263 cm^{-1} (N-H functional group, secondary amine), 1629 cm^{-1} (carbonyl group of lactams), and 1292 cm^{-1} (C-N). These peaks, along with the melting point, confirm the formation of product (1).

Various nitration methods were applied to synthesize the nitro derivative of compound (1) using $\text{HNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and $\text{KNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$. In one method, 0.3g KNO_3 and 0.5 mL H_2SO_4 were used for 6 hours on an ice bath, resulting in an orangish suspension. TLC showed Rf values of 0.43 for the product and 0.61 for the reactant, indicating increased polarity due to the nitro group. The nitronium ion (NO_2^+) was generated from the reaction of sulfuric acid and potassium nitrate, which then attacked the conjugated pi system of compound (1).

The nitration reaction took about 3 to 5 hours, with a resulting melting point of $245 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ and a yield of 65%. While the melting point was close to the literature value, the yield was moderate.

FTIR spectra of Compound 2a

Characterization of compound (2a) was done using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Key peaks include 1500 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of NO_2^+ and confirming nitration, and 1340 cm^{-1} , confirming the carbon-nitrogen bond. The carbonyl peak appeared at 1627 cm^{-1} .

In the second experiment, 0.5g of compound (1) was dissolved in acetone and stirred for 5 hours. This time, a different nitrating agent ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{HNO}_3$) was used. The solution turned yellow from orange. TLC showed R_f values of 0.60 for the reactant and 0.35 for the product, indicating increased polarity due to the nitro group. The reaction was conducted at 0°C to control fuming. The nitration yield improved to 80%, demonstrating that HNO_3 is a more effective nitrating agent than KNO_3 .

FTIR spectra of Compound 2b

Fourier Transform Infrared spectrum was used to characterize the product

(2b). The main peak for the conformation of nitration appeared at the frequency of

1500 cm^{-1} of above spectrum (3.3). The peak at the value of 3217 cm^{-1} showed the NH (Secondary amine) present in the ring. Peak at 1342 cm^{-1} indicate the carbon to nitrogen bond (C-N). The peak showed at 1622 cm^{-1} is the characteristic peak of carbonyl group (C=O)

Again, nitration of compound (1) was done same as above reaction (scheme 3.3) but for this time for reaction was increased from 5 to 6 hour to monitor the effects on yield and product appearance. Here again nitrating mixture ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{HNO}_3$) was used and prepared at 0°C . Nitronium ion which is strong nucleophile generated and reacted with sample (1) (Reaction 3.4). Color of solution becomes dark yellow from light orange. After 6 hours of constant stirring a TLC was performed to check the reaction progress. R_f values of reactant and product were calculated 0.60 and 0.30 respectively. It indicated that by the increasing the duration of reaction product (2c) become more and more polar. So, it is concluded that by increasing the duration of nitration polarity become increased therefore it might be possible that more than one position of benzene ring of sample (1) was nitrated. At the end of reaction product weighted and yield was calculated. Yield of product (2c) increased to 90%. Thus, by increasing the reaction time duration polarity and yield of product was increased.

Synthesis of Compound 2c

FTIR Spectra of Compound 2c

For the experiment (**2c**) characterization was done by Fourier Transform infrared spectrum. Peak at frequency value 3257 cm^{-1} showed the N-H functional group. The indication of Nitro group is done by the appearance of the peak at frequency 1556 cm^{-1} . Peak at 1350 cm^{-1} indicates the carbon to nitrogen bond (C-N). The peak the frequency value of 1624 cm^{-1} due to the carbonyl group (C=O).

After nitration of 2,2-dimethyl-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1*H*)-one the products were reduced by using different reducing agents and varying reaction condition to monitor the effects on the yield of amino products (**3a**), (**3b**), (**3c**), (**3d**) and (**3e**). Metal reducing agents used for reduction were: (i) $\text{SnCl}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (ii) Sn/HCl (iii) Zn/HCl (iv) $\text{Zn}/\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$.

In first reaction (**3a**) reduction of nitro compound was done with SnCl_2 in the presence of ethanol. Nitro compound with reducing agent SnCl_2 and ethanol was refluxed for 2.5 hours at 40°C (**Reaction 3.5**). Sn metal provide electrons and ethanol acts as proton source during reaction. After 2.5 hours a TLC was done to check the progress of reaction with the ratio of mobile phase as 5:5 n-hexane and Ethyl acetate. R_f values for reactant and product was 0.52 which showed the completion of reaction. After reaction completion product were extracted with Chloroform and left for evaporation. After evaporation of solvent a dark-gray type product (**3a**) collected that was not clear product and also yield was low for this reaction.

FTIR Spectrum of Compound 3a

Synthesis of Compound 3a

Fourier Transform Infrared spectrum of was used to characterize the compound (**3a**). The primary amine peaks usually appear at 3200-3300 cm^{-1} region with two peaks very near to each other. In above spectrum (**3.5**) two peaks were present in this spectrum of compound (**3a**) but these peaks were slightly away from each other at 3296 cm^{-1} , 3211 cm^{-1} . Peak present at 1629 cm^{-1} was due to carbonyl group present in heterocyclic moiety. The peak present at 1344 cm^{-1} showed the carbon to nitrogen bond (C-N).

In 2nd experiment (**3b**) Sn metal was used in the presence of few drops of hydrochloric acid for the reduction of nitro compound (**Reaction 3.6**). Sn metal acts as an electron source and drops of HCl acts as source of protons required for the reduction of nitro group. Reaction was refluxed for 3 hours at 0°C. Solution turns light yellow color from dark-gray by the addition of few drops of hydrochloric acid (HCl). R_f value was calculated as 0.48 which were different from nitro compound. After completion of reaction product was extracted by using chloroform as extraction solvent. A shing yellow colored product was collected after evaporation of solvent. Yield of product was 88% much better than above experiment.

Synthesis of Compound 3b

FTIR spectra of Compound 3b

The above I.R spectrum (**3.6**) was used to characterize the product (**3b**). Couple of peaks appeared at 3257 cm^{-1} and 3267 cm^{-1} was the clear indication of primary amine (NH_2) functional group. So, these peaks confirmed the reduction of nitro group to amino group. The peak at frequency 1622 cm^{-1} is due to carbonyl functional group ($\text{C}=\text{O}$). Peak appeared 1317 cm^{-1} was the indication of carbon to nitrogen bond functionality ($\text{C}-\text{N}$)

As already reduction was done in the presence of $\text{SnCl}_2/\text{ethanol}$ in first experiment but product (**3a**) was not clear and also FTIR peaks of primary amine was not satisfactory. Therefore, again SnCl_2 was used for reduction of nitro compound to amino (**Reaction 3.7**) in experiment (**3c**) in the presence of ethanol but this time reaction condition was changed like temperature was increased from 40°C to 75°C and reaction duration was also changed from 2.5 hours to 3.5 hours. Colored of solution was dark yellow this time, which. was extracted by using chloroform. After evaporation of solvent dark yellow product (**3c**) was collected and weighted. Melting point was $224\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$, which was satisfactory value. Yield of product was also good for

this reaction 88%. Therefore, we may conclude that by changing the reaction conditions like temperature and time yield of product was increased and also product becomes cleared.

FTIR Spectrum of Compound 3c

The above I.R spectrum (3.7) was used to characterize the product (3c). A couple of peaks shown at 3163 cm^{-1} and 3178 cm^{-1} were the characteristic peaks of primary amine (NH_2). Therefore, these two peaks confirmed that reduction of nitro compound to amino group was done efficiently. The other peaks were due to functional group present already in the moiety like the peak at 1622 cm^{-1} was due to the carbonyl group ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) present in heterocyclic structure. The peak at frequency value 1321 cm^{-1} was due to presence of carbon nitrogen bond ($\text{C}-\text{N}$) present in

structure.

In 4th experiment nitrated product was reduced by using Zn metal in the presence of HCl. Ethanol was used as solvent for this reaction. Nitrated sample with Zn in powdered form added in two neck flask and ethanol was mixed. Reaction was

refluxed for 3 Hours. During stirring of reaction few drops of hydrochloric acid (HCl) added due to which effervescence was observed. Zn metal act as an electron source and HCl as protons source for reduction of nitro compound to amino compound during this reaction (**Reaction 3.8**). At the end of reaction chloroform was used for the extraction of product (**3d**). A pale-yellow colored product was collected with the yield of 80%. This reaction was almost same as previous reduction with Sn metal in the presence of HCl.

FTIR spectra of Compound (3d)

Above infrared spectrum (**3.8**) was used to characterize the product (**3d**). Couple of peaks shown at the values of 3234 cm⁻¹ and 3251 cm⁻¹ was the characteristics peaks of primary amine (NH₂), Therefore these two peaks conformed the reduction of nitro compound to amino compound. The other peaks like at the frequency values of 1622 cm⁻¹ was due to the carbonyl group (C=O) present in heterocyclic moiety. The peak at 1315 cm⁻¹ was due to the presence of carbon to nitrogen bond present in the product (C-N).

In the last of experiment (**3**) reduction was done by using metal Zn in powdered form in the presence of solid NH₄Cl (**Reaction 3.9**). Ethanol was used as solvent for this reaction. Reaction was stirred for 1.5 hours at the temperature range of 75°C to 85°C. Colored of solution this time was dark. Product was extracted with chloroform.

After evaporation of solvent a black powdered form product (**3e**) collected and yield was calculated which was 71% not much higher.

FTIR spectra of Compound 3e

Synthesis of Compound 3e

The infrared spectrum of (**3.9**) was used to characterize the product (**3e**). The sign of reduction was indicated by the two peaks present very near to each other at frequency value of 3169 cm⁻¹ and 3197 cm⁻¹ those was the characteristic peaks of primary amine (NH₂). Carbonyl group peak was shown at the value of 1629 cm⁻¹. The peak at 1377 cm⁻¹ indicated the carbon to nitrogen bond (C-N).

Discussion

Quinazolinone, a significant heterocyclic compound, exhibits substantial structural flexibility and is recognized as an essential pharmacophore. Many of its derivatives are either directly used in medicine or serve as active ingredients. The 4-quinazolinone structure, with its fused nitrogen heterocyclic ring, has diverse biological importance, including anti-fungal, anti-malarial, anti-inflammatory, anti-tubercular, anti-HIV, anti-bacterial, anti-cancer, and analgesic properties. Due to its extensive medical applications, modifying the quinazolinone structure by derivatization to attach different groups is beneficial for obtaining improved results.

This study aimed to enhance the quinazolinone structure by synthesizing nitro and amino derivatives, followed by characterization using various analytical techniques. The initial synthesis of 2,2-dimethyl-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one involved using acetone and 2-

aminobenzamide with a Lewis acid catalyst. The resulting bright yellow solution yielded yellow crystals.

The FTIR spectrum of compound (1) confirmed the synthesis, displaying characteristic peaks such as N-H at 3263 cm⁻¹, carbonyl group at 1629 cm⁻¹, and C-N at 1292 cm⁻¹. Nitration of compound (1) was performed using different nitrating agents (HNO₃/H₂SO₄ and KNO₃/H₂SO₄) and varying conditions to optimize yield. The first nitration using KNO₃/H₂SO₄ yielded an orangish suspension, with an R_f value of 0.43 for the product and 0.61 for the reactant, indicating increased polarity due to the nitro group. However, the yield was only 65%. The FTIR spectrum of compound (2a) showed the nitro group peak at 1500 cm⁻¹, confirming nitration.

In the second experiment, changing the nitrating agent to HNO₃/H₂SO₄ improved the yield to 80%. The product's increased polarity was confirmed by the R_f value shift from 0.60 (reactant) to 0.35 (product). The FTIR spectrum of compound (2b) confirmed nitration with peaks at 1500 cm⁻¹ and 1340 cm⁻¹ for C-N bond. Increasing the reaction duration in the third experiment further improved the yield to 90%, with the FTIR spectrum of compound (2c) confirming nitration through peaks at 3257 cm⁻¹ (N-H), 1556 cm⁻¹ (NO₂), and 1350 cm⁻¹ (C-N).

The synthesized compounds' inhibitory potency (IC₅₀ values) against AChE (*Electrophorus electricus*) and BChE (*equine serum*) was evaluated. The nitro derivatives demonstrated good to moderate inhibition, with low micromolar IC₅₀ values. Derivatives with a 4-chlorophenyl group at the C-2 position of the quinazoline ring exhibited high AChE/BChE inhibitory activity. Similarly, compounds with di-isobutyl groups showed good inhibition, whereas those with an unsubstituted phenyl ring were less potent than their dinitro counterparts.

Conclusion:

This study successfully developed an efficient method for synthesizing amino derivatives of quinazolinone. Nitration of the quinazolinone moiety was initially performed using KNO₃ as the nitrating agent, followed by conventional nitration methods employing HNO₃ and H₂SO₄. The highest yield was achieved with the HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ combination. Reduction of the nitro group was most effectively achieved using tin metal in the presence of HCl. Future research will focus on synthesizing further derivatives of the amino product, including reactions with amino acids. These investigations aim to expand the pharmacological potential and application scope of quinazolinone derivatives in medicinal chemistry.

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